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CCS

PLATAFORMA MEXICANA
DE CAPTURA Y
ALMACENAMIENTO
DE CO₂

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Editorial Committee

Editor
Jazmín Mota

Editorial design
Héctor Ortega

Writing/collaboration
Paola García
Cecilia Rodríguez
David Montaña
Martín Haupt

Cover:
Unsplash

MeCCS
The Mexican Carbon Capture
and Storage Platform

<https://meccs.org.mx/>

✉ puntocritico@meccs.org.mx
🌐 [linkedin.com/company/meccs](https://www.linkedin.com/company/meccs)
📷 @MeCCS.plataforma

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Editor's note

Nowadays, it is easy to have almost anything we want at our fingertips; we only need a device that provides us access to many applications and websites that function as intermediaries between us and the world. Although there are significant benefits to the hyperconnection in which we live and which is advancing rapidly in a race to conquer markets, minds, and territory, we can encounter many challenges so that these platforms do not overtake us. As challenging as it may seem, the good news is that people continue to be the key behind technology. In this edition, we address the topic of human and digital platforms with a note by Paola García about the use of these tools to address sustainability issues and another by Cecilia Rodríguez and David Montaña about how platforms can help close gaps in education on energy and sustainability issues. At *CO2nversing*, we present you an interview with Igor Jiménez from Codek about platform design. We also share three infographics in *Yes, yes it is: platforms, what do networks tell us?*, and the MIT EN-Roads simulator. Finally, we leave you a list of suggestions and recommendations on this topic to *take away*.

Between the human and the digital: How do we address problems in sustainability?

By Paola Massyel García Meneses,
National Laboratory of Sustainability Sciences,
Institute of Ecology, UNAM

Generating trajectories towards sustainability involves introducing significant changes in multiple areas (infrastructures, policies, practices, behaviors). These changes unfold in the intricate landscape of wicked problems, where diverse perspectives and potential solutions intersect and collide. Moving toward more equitable and sustainable trajectories requires the recognition of diverse voices that collaborate in developing synergies between groups to achieve substantial change.

These projects require exploring various tools and methodologies to effectively obtain, transmit, and integrate ideas. Creating platforms and spaces for reflection is essential to generating a more significant impact as people participate in debates aimed at sharing and questioning the coherence of their projects while forging synergies, identifying shared objectives, and seeking to generate long-term results.

But what is a platform? The term "*platform*" can have several meanings depending on the context. It refers to a foundation or framework upon which something is built, operated, or conducted. For example, the platforms of transportation systems such as trains, aviation, and buses, or we could also think of continental or marine platforms in geological terms. In technology and computing, a platform typically refers to a combination of hardware and software components that provide a foundation for running applications or services. It includes the underlying infrastructure (such as processors, memory, storage, and networking components), the operating system, programming frameworks, libraries, and other tools. Computing platforms may vary in architecture, operating system, supported programming languages, and available development tools.

In sustainability, the need to establish connections between various sectors has driven the development of tools that act as facilitators to address the complexity of our challenges. These tools, whether platforms or other artifacts, function as bridges that link different worlds and help overcome boundaries¹. Although they can be tremendously effective, their digital nature can sometimes generate a certain coldness when using them. However, other tools in the field of sustainability also promote the creation of links but require a facilitation process - of one or several people in charge - for their implementation. Some examples are workshops, discussion tables, and focus groups, which are based on face-to-face interactions to encourage an active exchange of ideas and opinions and generate more significant participation from those involved.

Now... a set of people who have expert knowledge of a topic can also function as platforms, human platforms that drive actions. Although the term "*human platform*" does not have a universally recognized definition, it can also be interpreted according to its context. If we talk about social interactions or community building, a human platform can refer to a person or group of people who facilitates communication, collaboration and networking between individuals. These may be community leaders, influencers or organizers who play a key role in bringing people together and fostering connections. Regarding sustainability issues, these people are known as **change agents**².

On the other hand, in personal development, a human platform could refer to the individual themselves as the basis on which they build their skills, knowledge, and abilities. We can include mentors, coaches, or support networks that provide guidance and help achieve personal or professional, individual, or collective goals.

Both platforms (computational and human) have their strengths and weaknesses, but imagine the union of a human platform with a computational one! This duo could be the key to faster solving complex problems since, as people say, "*unity is strength.*"

At the National Laboratory of Sustainability Sciences, platforms are being developed to obtain, transmit and integrate ideas more effectively, collaboratively, co-produced and co-created. A team of academics and students are developing a metagraphic platform financed by the *Support Program for Research and Technological Innovation Projects* of UNAM³. This initiative intersects multiple projects, which form a cyber-human space designed to facilitate reflection -individual and collective- on the architecture of sustainability projects.

The PRISMA platform (Reflective Platform on Multi-Agency Sustainability Impacts for its acronym in Spanish) uses elements of the Theory of Change model⁴ and the causal networks approach to guide users in creating their own networks to represent their projects and visualize them graphically. Users can also link various projects and identify common points and actions, thus coordinating and promoting synergies between multiple initiatives.

1 Lee, C. P. (2005). Between chaos and routine: Boundary negotiating artifacts in collaboration. In H. Gellersen, K. Schmidt, M. Beaudouin-Lafon & W. Mackay (Eds.), *Proceedings of the ninth European conference on computer supported cooperative work* (pp. 387-406). New York, NY: Springer-Verlag.

2 Van Poeck, K., Læssøe, J., & Block, T. (2017). An exploration of sustainability change agents as facilitators of nonformal learning: Mapping a moving and intertwined landscape. *Ecology and Society*, 22(2).

3 Proyecto PAPIIT 2021-2024. TA300121 "Desarrollo de una plataforma para el análisis del impacto de proyectos de sostenibilidad en México"

4 Theory of Change is a model to identify and understand all the steps and conditions necessary to generate a significant and sustainable impact/change over time. It works as a visual tool to recognize what aspects we need to transform, but also how we plan for this transformation to occur within our communities. (Mayne, 2017).

Focused on versatility and accessibility, PRISMA allows multiple users to participate collaboratively and efficiently simultaneously. Although it is still in development, the platform has great potential to identify synergies between projects and invites interested audiences to collaborate in its construction since its code is open.

Although PRISMA is a platform on its own, it advocates collaborative work and the generation of human platforms. In the end, a computational tool can be very powerful, but we must remember that it is conceptualized, designed, built and managed by people. These tools help to make visible things that we sometimes do not perceive with the naked eye. Suppose we add a good manual, facilitator, or method to trigger reflection from a human platform. In that case, they will generate an impact that would be difficult to achieve in isolation.

In the era of artificial intelligence, where it seems that with a ChatGPT response, everything can be resolved and any doubt dispelled, we have to reflect more than ever on how much has been done, how much has been socio-environmentally destroyed, how many platforms we have at hand, and what we use them for, as well as how little they have served to build a better world. They have sold us - and we have bought - the idea that great technological developments will solve all problems, but it turns out that when these are complex and perverse, like those of sustainability, no computational platform or artificial intelligence can save us. There are many things that the digital world helps us with, but at the end of the day, we develop and implement them. So, human platforms are and have been the accurate catapult of all transformation processes. Why don't we take back these human structures and continue using technology? This duo can undoubtedly generate accelerated positive changes that last long term and unite us in intention and action.

PRISMA

Plataforma Reflexiva sobre
Impactos en Sostenibilidad
Multi-Agencial

Would you like to collaborate with us at PRISMA?

<https://codeberg.org/LANCIS-UNAM/prisma/>

Building bridges to the future

Educational platforms as a key element in closing gaps

By **Cecilia Rodríguez Gómez** and **David I. Montaña López**,
Energyou

In this era of technological advances with overwhelming speeds, we often ask ourselves, "*Where are we going?*" On the one hand, we may feel that the critical values of our very humanity are in danger, while on the other, pillars of hope are forming to resolve the significant challenges we face, such as gaps in education, the transformation of the energy and industrial sectors or the climate crisis. So, how do we move forward while creating synergies between human knowledge and computational platforms?

When answering this question, we should not ignore the benefits of this combination of knowledge. From our experience as creators and directors of ENERYOU, a digital energy and sustainability education platform, we consider that there are advantages worth highlighting:

- **Accessibility and democratization**

Computing platforms allow access to educational resources from anywhere globally (with some minimum technical requirements). Furthermore, personalising learning according to individual needs becomes feasible through recommendation algorithms and data analysis, avoiding falling into a generalized education model.

- **Simplifying complexities**

The complexity of energy and sustainability concepts can be simplified through data visualization. Computational platforms facilitate the creation of graphical representations that help to understand problems and their possible solutions better. In addition, they allow the processing, analysis and generation of information for decision-making in a faster and easier way.

- **Simulations and modeling**

The energy and environmental scenarios simulation allows students to represent and analyze the effects of different decisions and policies in these sectors. These hands-on experiences foster more profound understanding and greater motivation for action.

- **Remote collaboration**

Online learning platforms facilitate collaboration between students and experts worldwide, creating global knowledge networks that transcend geographic barriers.

In the search for solutions to address the climate crisis and promote routes towards sustainability, human knowledge and computational platforms emerge as crucial allies, playing complementary roles that enhance their impact. This marriage between the human and the digital is evident in the educational field, where technological platforms have become catalysts for awareness and action around various aspects of energy and sustainability.

A specific case is the educational platforms covered under the umbrella of the EdTech (Educational Technology) movement. As protagonists in this story, their role goes beyond the simple transmission of knowledge, as they have become engines of change and empowerment. These platforms not only address historical challenges in education, such as accessibility and personalization of learning, but are also actively committed to promoting more sustainable practices and a deep understanding of environmental issues.

EdTech platforms are shaping innovative and accessible learning experiences tailored to the individual needs of students and the context of the geographic regions where they are located. From interactive simulations to personalized courses, these educational solutions not only inform but also inspire and empower people to adopt more responsible practices in their daily lives, as well as in their professional careers or the organization they are part of.

But also, the integration of human knowledge and digital platforms extends beyond the educational field. For example, companies use data analysis tools in the business sector to optimize their operations and reduce their environmental footprint. Artificial intelligence and machine learning are used to identify energy efficiency opportunities and design more sustainable business strategies.

It is crucial to highlight that the relevance of sustainability issues and the digital era is not limited to just another trend or the interest of new generations. In a context where the transition to a sustainable future must be rapid and fair, addressing additional challenges, such as upskilling and reskilling in various sectors, is imperative. Bridging the gap in adopting new technologies and more sustainable practices becomes a priority to mitigate the effects of the climate crisis and build a more equitable, prosperous and resilient present and future.

In conclusion, a comprehensive proposal between human and computational platforms has great potential to address sustainability challenges today and in the future. In education, EdTech platforms provide innovative educational tools that inform, inspire, and empower people to make the necessary changes and actions to build a more just and sustainable world in which harmony between society and the environment is achievable.

Before closing this note, we leave some points for the readers to reflect on:

- *The double edge of technology.* Rapid technological evolution offers us powerful tools to address global challenges such as the climate crisis, but at the same time, it raises questions about the impact on our fundamental human values. It is crucial to find a balance between technological progress and the preservation of our humanity.
- *The need for holistic approaches.* Effectively solving complex problems like the climate crisis requires a holistic approach that combines human wisdom with the analytical power of technology. It is essential to transcend the divisions between these two fields to find comprehensive and sustainable solutions.
- *Ethical and moral challenges in the digital age.* As we move towards an increasingly interconnected and digitalized world, ethical and moral questions arise about the responsible use of technology. We must reflect on ensuring that technological progress aligns with our fundamental human values and promotes collective well-being.
- *Optimism in the face of adversity.* Despite our challenges, the human capacity to innovate and collaborate is a cause for hope. By joining forces between the human and the computational worlds, we can find creative and effective solutions to build a more prosperous and sustainable future for all.

ENERYOU

If you want to know more about EnergyYou as well as the courses and activities they have available, we invite you to consult the following link:

www.eneryou.org

CONVERSING

People and their realities: designing more accessible and inclusive platforms

Interview with **Igor Jiménez**, co-founder of Codek.
igor@co-deck.com / www.co-deck.com

By **Paola García**

Platforms are the future. They offer us answers, projections, the generation of augmented and virtual realities, and more. Platforms are frequently used to “connect” to and with people, to engage in conversations remotely and massively, but *how accessible and inclusive are they, and how can we ensure they are? What will be your role in future problem-solving?*

We talked about these and other topics with Igor Jiménez in this interview.

Igor is a visionary in interaction design and sustainability with a deep focus on soil regeneration and water management, applying his experience in business, especially in tourism. Trained in Audiovisual Media Arts, he has led innovations based on the human-centered design as the local leader of the *Interaction Design Foundation* in Mexico City. He founded Codek, a studio that redefines triple-impact design, incorporating gamification and behavior change techniques to promote sustainable solutions. His commitment to positive transformation extends to his work as a consultant advising companies on sustainability strategies from a systemic perspective to address complex challenges with innovative solutions that benefit both society and the environment. Igor stands out for his ability to create products and services that solve problems and foster a paradigm shift towards more sustainable and life-centered practices.

P. Igor, what does a platform mean to you?

I: For me, “platform” is a very broad concept. For example, in the field of computing, it was born from the development of hardware, where all computer activities were articulated. However, indeed, a platform does not necessarily have to be something related to computing; it also represents how people exchange ideas, knowledge, or even goods and/or relate.

Although the concept appears more related to technology, it is interesting how, with the development of computing, it has evolved to integrate social sciences into the design of these platforms. As soon as the technology developed a little more, the same programmers realized that they needed something more than cybernetics and that they had to put people more at the center of their design, giving rise to two fundamental disciplines: human-computer interaction and the user experience. Both integrate sociology, anthropology, ethnography, psychology, ergonomics and cognitive science around how the user will use the technology because technology by itself is nothing. Technology has taken on an excessive role in recent years, but it is a means to an end, not an end in itself.

Currently, many people use the internet and everything it contains to work and communicate. This is an undeniable and unavoidable reality, especially in the urban contexts of almost all countries. So, we have to be careful when we talk about technology because we are the privileged ones who live immersed in a technological life, and then some simply do not have access to it or the internet. Interestingly, today, an office without internet simply does not work. I remember that when I was a child, this type of technology did not exist; nevertheless, the world worked, but of course, it did so at a different pace.

There is a huge paradigm shift. The way we use information has changed. We no longer memorize things like before. Now, we know that everything is available and accessible on the Internet. There is a giant leap between generations. The new generations probably need to improve in terms of memory. Still, they can also work with much more information, at least for those who have access to the information and the means to consult it. This difference can also create a socio-technological lag.

It is a very complex and broad topic that should not be taken lightly, but a fascinating reflection in this sense is that of those excluded in this digital revolution and how, for those included, a cognitive paradigm shift occurs to which we could and perhaps should transcend as humanity, not as separate groups.

However, we can also create technology-connected communities, generate alternative economies, and decentralise knowledge, wealth, and people's relationships through the web. There are many more options than the digital monopolies that most of us use all the time, and the evolution of decentralization through socio-technological platforms interests me most.

P. So, how do you think inclusion and accessibility can be guaranteed on a platform?

I: Well, in design, accessibility is an issue that was a little forgotten at the beginning of platform development, but today, it is gaining more and more strength. It is important to define to what extent accessibility can be established or what we understand by accessibility because there are insurmountable limitations, especially related to inclusion rather than accessibility.

In general, when we talk about accessibility, we are referring to people with different abilities, and there are several scenarios: people who can access by voice, color-blind people (which is more or less 8% of the world's male population); We should also consider the different native languages of our country that are almost entirely forgotten on the platforms, they are practically not used. All in all, I believe that the most overlooked of all this global digitalization is the elderly group; even at the level of rights, I consider this group to be strongly violated, and I give an example with the identification of identity in financial entities, which in Mexico it is done through fingerprinting that is confirmed with the INE database (something very unusual if you think about it thoroughly). Well, it turns out that older people's fingerprints fade a little, and when they go to the bank to try to use financial services, they are the ones who have the most problems. It is complex to consider all these options when designing, especially because budgets are continuously optimized or intended to be efficient. Obviously, this design needs time to develop and design.

Finally, I would like to add that low-income people are seldom included in applications or platforms designed for specific tasks. It is complex to bridge this inclusion gap through design, but often, ethnographies or in-depth studies on user habits make it possible to find artifacts or means by which these differences can be addressed or at least soften digital friction. We have designed a platform for learning agroecological techniques, and the big problem was precisely that farmers do not usually use specific technology; they typically listen to the radio or the word as a means of transmitting knowledge. So, although we leave the written option, we also look for a spoken option to include them or facilitate access to knowledge. In summary, I believe that the way to guarantee accessibility is by deeply understanding the user.

P. What approaches do you use to develop platforms in the field of sustainability and why?

I: When reflecting on sustainable design, we question whether sustainability is currently sufficient and comprehensive, asking precisely what we want to maintain: resources and our way of life. The question guides towards the idea of regenerative design, which seeks not only to preserve but also to enrich and renew, creating an impact beyond its immediate limits. This approach is oriented towards self-renewal and continuous updating, avoiding obsolescence.

We focus on three key areas to generate regenerative impact: economy, education, and habit change. Theories of behavior change and gamification support the latter to stimulate positive individual transformations that contribute to the collective. We differentiate education as the construction of tools and models to integrate knowledge into daily life, from the promotion of changes in habits that lead to collective impacts.

In the economic field, our objective is to improve the efficiency of resources in companies with impact, designing or reinventing business models towards regenerative practices. We adopt and promote systems thinking and System B theory of change, focusing on regenerative solutions that benefit socially, economically and environmentally, moving away from exclusively extractive or unilateral benefit approaches. This commitment to comprehensive well-being seeks, ultimately, to foster communities through collaboration and constant addition of value, following the principle of always contributing positively to clients, colleagues, and society in general.

P. Do you think these tools will be the future?

I: Predicting the future is complex, especially with the increasing dependence on technology, which makes it easier to conceive of a future with digitalization or platforms. This situation presents a paradox: although technology alone is not the solution to our problems, it is a powerful means that offers the possibility of transforming the world and the economy and creating communities through knowledge networks and decentralized knowledge. This potential is especially relevant in our Cartesian world, characterized by centralization, hierarchization and masculinization, suggesting that technology may be essential to changing these patterns.

An example of this change is the possibility of developing decentralized economies through technologies such as blockchain and alternative currencies. However, another paradox arises: if the creation of these technologies responds to a need for more trust between people. While blockchain facilitates decentralization, it is also suggested that it is not essential to achieve it, as demonstrated by examples of currencies developed without these technologies. Still, the ubiquitous presence of digital technology in our lives and economies makes it difficult to imagine a future without it, highlighting that any future innovation will likely be based on the technological elements we have today.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

PLATFORMS

The concept of “platform” is a metaphor for transportation platforms (air, railway, etc.), but the magnitude they have reached makes them more similar to those of the geological context (continental, glaciers).

Their expansion resembles the formation of supercontinents where several portions of land drift slowly until agglomerating into a large continental mass.

Amasia
The next supercontinent

The platforms have a network structure

The first representations of networks were those of streets, drains and sewers.

In 1954, J.A. Burns introduced the concept of social networks as systems of human relationships based on emotional ties.

From 2010 to 2020, the number of digital platforms has quintupled, but **70%** of the revenue goes to two countries: United States and China.

They can be physical, digital or human

Corporate networks in the physical world respond to a logic of growth and expansion; **none have desired to have limits or be local.**

References:

- News ONU: <https://news.un.org/es/story/2021/02/1488562>
- Podcast Solaris: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HRymVYRxjJM>

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

What do the networks tell us?

Network science provides valuable information about the relationship between people and/or things.

In a research developed between 2021 and 2023*, network theory was used to uncover the narratives of people from different regions and backgrounds about Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS).

The study allowed participants to create cognitive maps represented as networks and, from them, explore the narratives behind their ideas and perceptions.

Same elements, diverse narratives

Diverse perceptions, different outcomes

Narratives and positions about CCS

“CCS is a technology that...

...contributes to sustainability”

Greenhouse gases are a consequence of many human activities related to economic development. Its control through CCS can help building more sustainable routes if research and technological improvement are supported and accompanied by regulation and incentives such as carbon markets. The integration of social aspects and other environmental impacts are essential.

...helps industrial decarbonization”

Some industries can only reduce their emissions with technologies like CCS. These industries (cement, steel, chemicals) are essential for our daily activities. A cluster approach would allow several industries to share infrastructure, expenses and risks and reduce their emissions. However, there are market, political and social dynamics that determine the viability of such projects. Regulation, market rules and operational aspects are critical.

...focusses on economic development”

Although CCS proposes the reduction of emissions in the industry, its introduction can have social and economic implications. There is a strong focus on employing this technology in highly polluting industries that are not necessarily seeking transformations towards sustainability but the continuity of their activities. On the other hand, CCS can create new business areas, new products and jobs.

Considered aspects for building the maps:

- Sustainability
- Technicians
- Sociopolitical
- Economical

* This work is in the process of review and publication, if you want more information about it, write to J.Mota@sms.ed.ac.uk.

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

Climate change simulator

Model your project or policy

An online simulator to test and explore cross-sector climate solutions.

It allows making connections between the things you care about and the possibilities available to help ensure a resilient future.

Users can quickly see the long-term effects of the global climate policies and actions they envision.

Primary energy sources

Net Greenhouse Gas emissions

Scenario Increase in temperature by 2100

- +21,000 Equations
- < 60 milliseconds response time
- +340,000 people participated in events
- +164 countries reached
- 20 available languages (incl. Spanish)

Check En-ROADS here:
<https://www.climateinteractive.org/en-roads/>

Sustainability Initiative

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In this section, we leave you a list of suggestions and recommendations that include several platforms that combine the human and technological components, as well as some podcasts, series and books that will continue to nourish your interest in this topic.

MeCCS

The Mexican CCS Platform is a communication, dissemination and exchange project of knowledge and information about Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technology and its role in sustainable development in Mexico. It seeks to facilitate and promote the link between different actors and sectors that participate in decision-making and in the design and implementation of projects and policies related to this technology.

<https://www.meccs.org.mx/>

ENERYOU

Energyou is an EdTech specialized in energy and sustainability whose objective is to create an easy and accessible digital learning community to enhance the formation of human capital for the energy transition.

<https://energyou.org/>

Platform: Geocomunes

Geocomunes is a collective that works for accompanying towns, communities, neighbourhoods, colonies or organizations in the fight to defend common goods through the production of maps for analysis and dissemination to strengthen collective organization from below. They map conflicts caused by the degradation, privatization and dispossession of common goods, as well as "infrastructure" projects built with the purpose of capital continuing to accumulate.

<https://www.geocomunes.org/>

Podcast SOLARIS: Platforms

This episode of the Solaris podcast discusses the origin of platforms and how the technology behind them has colonized us. It addresses platform capitalism, video surveillance, and WeChat to understand the keys to this metamorphosis.

<https://open.spotify.com/episode/6rLIKE2nzhzDAajdltpsCT>

PARA LLEVAR

TAKE-AWAY

Book: *Homo Deus, a brief history of tomorrow*

In this bestseller, Yuval Noah Harari discusses how technological disruption is transforming and will change the world. Harari explores the projects, dreams, and nightmares shaping the 21st century—from overcoming death to creating artificial intelligence.

<https://www.lecturalia.com/libro/98343/homo-deus>

Podcast: *Decrypting sustainability - Interview with Jazmín Mota*

In this episode of Eneryou's *Decrypting Sustainability* podcast, you will find an interview with Jazmín Mota, founder and member of MeCCS, who talks about CO2 Capture and Storage technology from her own vision and experience.

<https://open.spotify.com/episode/3YIGezNuONSaGZE5jdgCpJ?si=d807322a387b434e>

Serie: *Black Mirror*

Black Mirror is a British dystopian science fiction anthology television series created by Charlie Brooker. Each episode has a different tone, environment, and even reality, but all present strong criticism of how combining technology and society can lead us to live in unimaginable ways, although many are current.

<https://www.netflix.com/title/70264888>

Platform: *NuestroFuturo-NuestraEnergía (OurFuture-OurEnergy)*

This platform is a space for analysis and articulation promoted by more than twenty-five organizations, civil society movements, cooperatives, workers and academics from Mexico who reflect on possible paths towards a generation, distribution and consumption model of common and fair energy with the people and nature.

<https://nuestrofuturo-nuestraenergia.org/>

Mexico City, Mexico, 2024